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UAV in Monitoring and Evaluating Infrastructural Projects: Awareness and Extent of Adoption Study

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Abstract

An unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV), also called a drone, has been gaining attention globally to solve different tasks. This study specifically sought to investigate the current level of awareness and extent of UAV adoption in monitoring and evaluating infrastructural projects. The study used a descriptive, quantitative and qualitative research design methods of investigation, as well as a stratified and random sampling technique to select a sample size from a population of 802 practitioners in the three (3) regions of Nigeria. The data collection and survey instrument included a well-structured questionnaire, semi-structured discussions, personal observations and visits to elicit information from respondents and infrastructural projects. The collected data was presented using frequency distribution in the form of tables, charts via IBM SPSS Statistics version 26.0. While Mean value score was used to analyse the study's main objectives. The study's findings indicate that there is a low level of awareness and extent of UAV adoption in monitoring and evaluating infrastructural projects across Nigeria, given that a moderate and low mean values obtained from the respondents depicting a low level of awareness of UAV adoption in infrastructural project monitoring and evaluation. This study recommends that, there should be concerted effort geared towards ensuring that some level of intense awareness is created towards the adoption of UAV. Effort should be made towards ensuring the cost of acquiring UAV are subsidized and made available for industry players to access easily

Keywords: Awareness, Infrastructural projects, Nigeria, Mean value score, Monitoring, Unmanned aerial vehicle.

1. Introduction

Nigeria's infrastructural development landscape is undergoing significant transformation, with numerous high-profile projects aimed at bridging the country's infrastructure gap. However, the effective monitoring and evaluation of these projects pose a significant challenge, particularly in the face of limited resources, geographical constraints, and the need for real-time data. In recent years, Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), also known as drones, have emerged as a game-changer in the infrastructure sector, offering unparalleled capabilities for aerial surveillance, inspection, and monitoring. They offer a potential solution to the limitations and inefficiencies associated with traditional monitoring and evaluation methods (Alizadehsalehi & Yitmen 2019). Potentially the integration of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) in monitoring infrastructural projects have presented an opportunity for enhanced supervision. Unmanned Aerial Vehicle have the capacity to save time, improves accessibility to compromised spaces, saves cost,

reduces safety concerns and can be applied in projects monitoring and evaluation to facilitate progress monitoring, site mapping and surveying, building inspection and safety management (Albeaino & Gheisari 2021).

The adoption of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) in Nigeria's infrastructure sector remains underexplored, despite their potential benefits. While research has delved into the technical aspects and applications of UAVs, the level of awareness and adoption among key stakeholders in Nigeria has received insufficient attention.

Previous studies have highlighted a lack of awareness and understanding among key stakeholders about the benefits and potential of UAVs in monitoring and evaluating infrastructural projects in Nigeria (Ikuabe et al., 2022). Bolaji, Olatunde, Valentine., & Fatai (2024) also identified lack of awareness as the most significant factors that limit the use of UAVs in infrastructural project.

This limited awareness hinders the recognition of UAVs as valuable tools in the industry (Liang et al., 2023). Furthermore, research has shown that while 66% of respondents are aware of UAVs in construction monitoring, only 51% have adopted them in various construction sectors, and a mere 17.6% have adopted UAVs for safety and security monitoring (Okaka et al., 2020).

From this study it can be seen that the adoption of UAV is low and the level of awareness of potential of the innovative technology is also low. The study is also limited because it only focused on Enugu metropolis and cannot be used to ascertain the current level of awareness and level of adoption of UAVs by practitioners and key stakeholders in Nigeria. The current literature reveals a significant gap in geographical limitations by (Okaka et al., 2020) and (Bolaji et al., 2024)

This research gap highlights the need for further investigation, to carry out a study that will ascertain the true level of UAVs awareness and level of adoption in Nigeria's infrastructure sector, with a focus on practical applications and stakeholder engagement. The objectives of this study is to investigate the current level of awareness and extent of UAVs adoption in monitoring and evaluating infrastructural projects across Nigeria with a focus on practitioners in key regions such as Rivers-state, Lagos, and Abuja.

The geographical scope of the study will cover infrastructure projects in Rivers State, Abuja and Lagos. Content scope of the study is limited to the Investigation on the current level of awareness and extent of application of UAV adoption in monitoring and evaluating infrastructural projects.

2. Literature review

2.1 Infrastructural Project

According to Investopedia, infrastructure is defined as the basic physical systems of a business, region, or nation and often involves the production of public goods or production processes. Instances of infrastructure encompass transportation systems, communication networks, sewage facilities, water supply systems, and educational establishments. Bamidele, Adenusi, & Osunsanmi, 2016; Ogunsanya, Fanu & Oladipo (2016) defined Infrastructure as the fundamental facilities and systems of a country, region community or area, entailing large-scale public systems, services, and facilities that are necessary for economic activity, including power and water supplies, public transportation, telecommunications, roads, sewer systems, public works and schools.

According to Fulmer and Jeffery (2009) Infrastructure is the set of facilities and systems that serve a country, city, or other area and encompasses the services and facilities necessary for its economy, households and firms to function. Infrastructure is composed of public and private physical structures such as roads, railways, bridges, tunnel, sewers, electric grids and telecommunication.

According to Utin (2024), a project is a temporary endeavour designed to produce a unique product, service or result with a defined beginning and end (usually time-constrained and often constrained by funding or deliverables) undertaken to meet unique goals and objectives, typically to bring about beneficial change or added value. The key characteristics that a projects must have is, a project must have a specific start and end date, they are not ongoing efforts like operations, each project results in a unique deliverable, which could be a product, service, or other result and projects are often developed in steps and continue to evolve as more information becomes available.

2.2 Monitoring and Evaluation of Infrastructural Projects

Project monitoring is a systematic process of tracking, reviewing, and regulating the progress and performance of a infrastructural project to ensure it stays on course and meets its objectives. It involves continuously gathering data, analysing performance metrics, and comparing actual progress against the project plan. Project monitoring encompasses essential components such as data gathering, change control, quality control, performance measurement, progress reporting, issue identification and resolution, change control and risk management (Dizon & Sonza 2023). Infrastructural project monitoring is an ongoing process that spans the entire project lifecycle, from initiation to closure. Effective project monitoring helps in ensuring that the project stays aligned with its goals, maintains stakeholder satisfaction, and achieves its desired outcomes within the agreed constraints of time, cost, and quality.

Project evaluation is a systematic process of assessing a project's performance and outcomes to determine its effectiveness, efficiency, and impact. It involves collecting and analyzing data to understand how well the project has met its objectives, identify lessons learned, and provide recommendations for future projects (Erzaij, Rashid, Naji, & Ali 2020). Objectives of project evaluation are: assessing achievement of goals, Measuring the impact on stakeholders and the community, including any unintended consequences, to examine how resources (time, money, personnel) were used and whether they were used optimally, Identifying lessons learn and providing accountability: to demonstrate to stakeholders, including funders and beneficiaries, how the project was managed and what it achieved.

2.3 Tools to aid project monitoring and evaluation

There are some project management tools are essential for successful project delivery, providing structure, guidance, and organization throughout the project lifecycle. Here are some common tools that can be used during project monitoring and evaluation in construction:

2.3.1 Gantt Chart

Gantt chart is a powerful visual tool used for planning, tracking, and managing projects (Wilson, 2003). It is prominent when tracking the progress and performance of ongoing projects. Gantt chart is a horizontal bar chart that visually represents a project schedule. It displays tasks or activities along the y-axis and time in the x-axis. Each task is represented by a bar, whose length corresponds to the duration and its position indicates the start and end dates. According to Huang, Tory, Staub-French and Pottinger (2009), the benefits of Gantts charts in project monitoring and evaluation are visual representations, illustrating task dependencies, resource allocation, progress tracking.

2.3.2 Earned Value Analysis (EVA)

EVA analysis is a robust control technique that enables project managers to effectively monitor and manage project expenses and schedules (Chou, Chen, Hou, & Lin, 2010). With the use of EVA, one can determine the deviations from project plan and can take proper corrective actions (Hazır, 2015). Naderpour & Mofid (2011) defined EVM as a widely acceptable methodology that assesses project performance and seamlessly integrates it with cost and Schedule metrics, providing a comprehensive framework for project evaluation and management. There are three key parameters of EVA required to measure project performance namely planned value (PV), actual cost (AC) and earned value (EV) (Utin, 2024). Earned Value Analysis (EVA) is a performance analysis method that compares the scheduled amount of work (planned value) with the achieved amount of work (earned value) and (actual cost) at a point in time. It integrates project scope, schedule, and cost measures to provide a comprehensive view of project health. By comparing the value of work accomplished. From theses three pieces of data, performance can be trended, and metrics calculated to express the status of the project. It helps project managers track progress, identify variances and make informed decisions. Table 1 shows the basic EVM metrics, Table 2 shows the performance indicators and variances in the EVM and Table 3 shows the forecast indicators in the EVM technique.

Table 1: Basic EVM metrics (Novinsky et al., 2018)

METRICS	INTERPRETATION
Planned Value (PV)	Indicates the approved budget for work scheduled to be completed by a specified date or simply budgeted cost of work scheduled (BCWS)
Earned Value (EV)	Indicates the value of work completed as of a specified date or simply budgeted cost of work performed (BCWP)

Actual Cost (AC)	Indicates the costs incurred for work completed as of a specified date or simply actual cost of work performed (ACWP)
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Table 2: Performance indicators and variances in the EVM (Novinsky et al., 2018)

METRICS	FORMULA	INTERPRETATION
Cost Variance (CV)	$CV = EV - AC$	A variance that shows whether a project is below (positive) or above (negative) budget.
Schedule Variance (SV)	$SV = EV - PV$	A variance that shows whether a project is ahead of (positive) or behind (negative) schedule.
Cost Performance Index (CPI)	$CPI = EV/AC$	This index measures the efficiency with which economic resources are used. If it is less than 1, the project has a higher actual cost than budgeted (cost overrun); if it is equal to 1, the project has an actual price equal to the projected cost; and if it is greater than 1, the project has a lower actual cost than budgeted
Schedule Performance Index (SPI)	$SPI = EV/PV$	An index that measures efficiency in the use of time. If it is less than 1, the project is behind schedule; if it is equal to 1, the project is on schedule, and if it is greater than 1, the project is ahead of schedule.
Cost Variance (VAC%)	$VAC = (BAC - EAC)/BAC$	Indicates the variance in the final cost of the project with respect to the original.

Table 3: Forecast indicators in the EVM technique (Novinsky et al., 2018)

METRICS	FORMULA	INTERPRETATION
Estimated cost to complete the project (ETC)	$ETC = (BAC - EV)/CPI$	Estimated cost required to complete the remainder of the project.
Estimated cost at project completion (EAC)	$EAC = AC + (BAC - EV)/CPI$	Indicates how much the project will cost in the end if the cost performance index (CPI) remains the same

2.4 Unmanned Aerial Vehicle

Unmanned aerial vehicle is an aircraft that is remotely controlled. It is an aircraft that operates without a human pilot on board. UAVs are remotely controlled or fly autonomously through pre-programmed flight plans, using on-board sensors, GPS and navigation system. The inherent aerial superiority and data acquisition capabilities, render the unmanned aerial vehicle a feasible instrument, providing a spectrum of advantages spanning from on-site security to remote surveillance (Moret, 2018). Table 4 shows vehicle types and comparison as well as the advantages and disadvantages

Table 4: Comparisons of Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (Hassanalian & Abdelkef, 2017)

VEHICLE TYPES	ADVANTAGES	DISADVANTAGES	APPLICATION
Multi-Rotor	Ease to operate and fly, Less expensive	Fewer flight times, Short endurance	Good for Ariel Photography and Ariel surveillances
Fixed-Wing	Long endurance, Larger distance coverage, High in Speed	Expensive, Need training to operator	Good for Ariel mapping, Pipeline and power line inspection
Single Rotor	Long endurance, High Payload capacity, High in Speed	Expensive, Need training to operator More dangerous	Ariel Laser Scanning
Fixed Wing – Hybrid	Long endurance, Hover	Not mature	Drone delivery

2.4.1 Unmanned Aerial Vehicle Onboard Equipment

UAV on-board equipment refers to the various devices or equipment that can be installed on the UAVs to collect data, conduct surveillance and perform specific task. Some of the common UAV on-board equipment are cameras, sensors LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging), radio transmitters, payloads, navigation system etc. As seen below is Table 5, which shows the on-board equipment used by unmanned aerial vehicle and their description.

Table 5: Unmanned Aerial Vehicle on-board equipment (Albeaino & Gheisari 2021)

ONBOARD EQUIPMENT	DESCRIPTION
Visual Cameras	Used to collect regular images and videos
Thermal Cameras	Thermographic cameras that sense infrared radiation. Collect radiation with longer wavelengths than visible light.
LiDARs and Laser Scanners	Capture surface shapes of objects or buildings by using a line of laser beams. Used to generate digital 3D representations of objects.
Radio Frequency Identification Readers	An automatic identification and data capture sensor. Used to identify, track, and collect information pertaining to objects

2.5 Awareness and adoption of UAV in monitoring Infrastructural Project

Awareness refers to the state of being informed or knowledgeable about something such as a concept, idea, product, service or technology. It involves having a clear understanding or perception of something including its characteristics, benefits and limitation while, Adoption is the process of accepting and integrating a new technology, product or innovation into existing practices, workflow or daily life.

In the context of UAV technology in monitoring infrastructural projects, awareness includes: knowledge of UAV technology and its capabilities, understanding of the benefits and limitations of using UAVs in infrastructural project monitoring, familiarity with UAV-related regulations and standards, recognition of its potential applications and use cases of UAVs in infrastructural project monitoring.

Increasing awareness is an important step in adopting new technologies, as it helps to educate stakeholders about the benefits and limitations of UAVs technology, address misconceptions, encourage considerations and adoption of UAV technology and facilitate informed decision making about UAV adoption and implementation.

Okaka et al., (2020) identified that there is lack of awareness of UAV capabilities by practitioners in infrastructural project and low adoption of UAV also in monitoring infrastructural projects in Nigeria. Knowledge and information on capacity of UAVs /User awareness of technology is one of the critical factors that affect the adoption of UAV in monitoring infrastructural project (Keong et al., 2023; Malak et al., 2022).

Study carried out by (Bolaji, Olatunde, Valentine., & Fatai 2024) also identified lack of awareness as the most significant factors that limit the use of UAVs in infrastructural project. Saving time, improving accessibility to compromised spaces and reducing cost while accomplishing construction tasks were highly regarded as UAVs implementation benefits in monitoring and evaluating infrastructural project (Albeaino & Gheisari 2021).

Overall, the level of awareness of UAV capabilities plays a crucial role in determining the adoption and effective implementation of UAVs in monitoring infrastructural projects.

Table 6 below are some of the application of UAV in infrastructural project monitoring and evaluation

Table 6: application of UAV in infrastructural project monitoring and evaluation

S/N	APPLICATIONS	CITATION
1	Volumetric estimation utilizing UAVs with laser scanner combined with standard topography survey 3D model of large area with software's like Pix4D and we can be able to calculate what type of earthwork and their quantities present at site and we can also take observation on past progress and plan data to identifying what earthwork has been removed and how much work is done on particular site and what duration.	Jadon, Anamika & Damini (2020)
2	Construction project monitoring /progress reporting/productivity monitoring/building inspection using UAVs on their sites to get real time work progress at site. To identify what is done which work is still pending on	Jadon et al., (2020) Okaka et al., (2020) Onososen et al., (2023) Tatum & Liu (2017)

	site and how the work is being executed	Fan & Saadeghvaziri (2019) Yıldız et al., (2021) Mosly (2017) Zhou & Gheisari (2018) Albeaino, et al.,(2019) Albeaino & Gheisari (2021)
3	Structural integrity maintenance sometimes clients may want to see images directly on their desktop of maintenance activities, so we can show them taken action on work from site to directly on their computer screen at office with the use of UAVs.	Jadon et al., (2020) Onososen et al., (2023) Zhou & Gheisari (2018)
4	Safety compliance by utilizing UAVs to inspect areas that are difficult to reach and monitor the compliance of workers as regards usage of personal protective equipment	Jadon et al., (2020) Okaka et al., (2020) Tatum & Liu (2017) Yıldız et al., (2021) Mosly (2017) Zhou & Gheisari (2018) Albeaino, et al.,(2019) Albeaino & Gheisari (2021)
5	Inventory management To keeping eye on site material, equipment's is most challenging task. Using live images, videos that is captured by UAV can help contractor keep eye on assets.	Jadon et al., (2020) Onososen et al., (2023) Tatum & Liu (2017) Mosly (2017) Albeaino & Gheisari (2021)
6	Quality assurance/damage detection and assessment Inspection of building, location of construction defects, scan the whole structure and create 3D image of the structure	Jadon et al., (2020) Yıldız et al., (2021) Mosly (2017) Zhou & Gheisari (2018) Albeaino & Gheisari (2021)
7	Site communication project team and employees can address different aspects of site operations with a software glance of its live data from drones. This type of transparency can lead to, simplification and coherence in decision making and production control, increased work coordination, easier identification of problems and deviation, stimulation of contacts among work units and broadened employee engagement and autonomy.	Jadon et al., (2020) Mosly (2017) Albeaino & Gheisari (2021)
8	Surveying and mapping	Okaka et al., (2020) Onososen et al., (2023) Tatum & Liu (2017) Mosly (2017) Zhou & Gheisari (2018) Albeaino & Gheisari (2021)
9	Security surveillance	Okaka et al., (2020) Tatum & Liu (2017) Yıldız et al., (2021) Mosly (2017) Albeaino & Gheisari (2021)

3. Methodology

To investigate the current level of awareness and extent of UAV adoption in monitoring and evaluating infrastructural project. The study utilized questionnaire and in-depth interview as data collection Instrument to gather quantitative/qualitative data from a representative sample of key industry stakeholders (project managers, civil engineers, UAV technology experts, government officials and industry decision makers) in Abuja, Rivers-state and Lagos involved in infrastructure projects in Nigeria, about their awareness of UAVs and current level of usage in monitoring and evaluating infrastructural projects.

The questionnaire consist of two sections, section A and B where the former addressed the demographic information of respondents and the later addressed the main objective of the study. A 5-point Likert scale

questionnaire was developed utilising knowledge obtained from relevant articles and journals reviewed earlier in previous section to gather data relevant to the intent of the research.

Based on the location and demography of the participants in the population, stratified random sampling is utilized for this study as it allows for selection of participants from different strata or subgroups based on key characteristics.

To ensure the validity of the instruments (Questionnaire), the study subjected the instruments to face-to-face validity by giving it to professional statisticians, scholars and the researcher’s supervisors. To test the reliability of the instrument, Cronbach alpha was utilized to analyze the data collected from the respondents.

Descriptive analysis chosen for this study frequency, mean and percentage. The frequency and percentage will be used to classify level of awareness of UAV concept among construction stakeholders and the mean was used to analyse the extent of UAV adoption in monitoring and evaluating infrastructural projects.

4. Results

Practitioners from infrastructure project firms working in the three (3) major cities of Abuja, Lagos and Port-Harcourt completed the self-administered questionnaires. Among the total of 266 professionals, 262 completed and submitted the questionnaires, while 251 were found to be fit for the analysis proper resulting in a response rate of 95.80%. The substantial response rate of 95.80% facilitated the acquisition of sufficient data that could be extrapolated to ascertain the realization of the research objectives set *ab ini tio*. The response rates are displayed in table 7.

Table 7 Sample Used from Population

LOCATION	POPULATION (N)	PERCENTAGE (%)	SAMPLE SIZE (n)	SAMPLE RETURNED	SAMPLE USED
Rivers-state	300	37.4	99	98	90
Abuja	252	31.4	84	82	81
Lagos	250	31.2	83	82	80
Total	802	100	266	262	251

4.1 Demographic responses

In the first section of the questionnaire the respondent’s characteristics as regards their nationality, discipline, years of experience, qualifications as well as types of infrastructural projects executed etc are presented.

4.2. Number of employees

On the number of employees in the respective infrastructure project firms as released by the respondents are as shown in the figure below. The figure shows that 148 (58.96%) were having in their employ about less than 150 employees, while 66 (26.29%) were having in their employ about more than 250 employees, 37 (14.74%) were having in their employ above 350 employees.

Figure 1: Number of employees

4.3. Nationality of respondents

The figure below shows the nationality of all the respondents of which 221 (88.05%) are Nigerians, while 30 (11.95%) are foreigners.

Figure 2: Nationality of respondents

4.4. Respondents discipline

In terms of the respondent's discipline, 38 (15.14%) are project managers, 43 (17.13%) are engineers, 52 (20.72%) are architects, 40 (15.94%) are quantity surveyors, 51 (20.32%) builders, while others are 27 (10.76%).

Figure 3: Respondents discipline

4.5. Respondents years of experience in the industry

The figure below depicts the experience of the respondents in the industry. 32 (12.75%) of the respondents have spent 1-5years, 45 (17.93%) spent 6-10 years, 52 (20.72%), 11-15 years, 103 (41.04%) 16-20 years, while 19 (7.57%) over 21 years.

Figure 4: Respondents years of experience in the industry

4.6. Respondents academic qualification

The figure below shows the academic qualifications of the respondents. 12 (4.78%) had NCE/ND as qualification. 148 (58.96%) had HND/B.Sc/B.Eng, 84 (33.47) had MBA/M.Sc as qualification, while 7 (2.79%) had Ph.Ds.

Figure 5: Respondents academic qualification

4.7. Specific types of infrastructure projects executed

On the types of infrastructure projects executed by the respondents, the figure below shows that 174 (69.32%) were building related infrastructure projects, 38 (15.14%) are road related infrastructure projects, 22 (8.76%) bridge-related infrastructure projects, while other-related infrastructure projects consist of 17 (6.77%).

Figure 6: Specific types of infrastructure projects executed

4.8. Sources of funding for infrastructure project

The figure below shows the sources of funding of the infrastructure projects. 114 (45.42%) were privately funded, while 137 (54.58) were publicly funded.

Figure 7: Sources of funding for infrastructure project

4.2 The current level of awareness and extent of UAV adoption in monitoring and evaluating infrastructural projects

The mean ranking of the current level of awareness and extent of UAV adoption in monitoring and evaluating infrastructural projects was conducted as shown in the table below.

Table 8: Current level of awareness and extent of UAV adoption

Descriptive Statistics						Ranking	Level of adoption
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation		
Are you aware of the capabilities of Unmanned Aerial Vehicle in Infrastructural Project Monitoring and Evaluation	251	1.00	5.00	2.3984	1.50487	1	Moderate
Have you ever used UAV in Infrastructural Project Monitoring and Evaluation	251	1.00	5.00	1.8924	1.17999	4	Low
Can you operate an Unmanned Aerial Vehicle	251	1.00	5.00	2.0120	1.35494	3	Low
Have you seen an unmanned aerial vehicle before	251	1.00	5.00	2.0518	1.27488	2	Low
Valid N (listwise)	251						

Based on table 4.2 above, the level of awareness and extent of UAV adoption with the highest mean ranking is “Are you aware of the capabilities of unmanned aerial vehicle in infrastructural project monitoring and evaluation?”, with a “moderate” mean value of 2.40. This indicates that practitioners working on infrastructure projects are moderately aware of the capabilities of unmanned aerial vehicle in infrastructural project monitoring and evaluation. The second highest mean ranking is “Have you seen an unmanned aerial vehicle before” with a “low” mean value of 2.05, denoting that the infrastructure project practitioners have seen an unmanned aerial vehicle used to enhance infrastructure project performance. “Can you operate an unmanned aerial vehicle” ranked at the third place, with a “low” mean value of 2.01. The level of awareness and extent of UAV adoption with the least mean ranking is “Have you ever used UAV in Infrastructural Project Monitoring and Evaluation”, with a “low” mean value of 1.89. Therefore, it is considered the least level of awareness and extent of UAV adoption in infrastructure projects.

4.3 Discussions

On the number of employees in the respective infrastructure project firms as released by the respondents. The figure shows that 148 (58.96%) were having in their employ about less than 150 employees, while 66 (26.29%) were having in their employ about more than 250 employees, 37 (14.74%) were having in their employ above 350 employees. On the nationality of all the respondents, 221 (88.05%) are Nigerians, while 30 (11.95%) are foreigners. In terms of the respondent's discipline, 38 (15.14%) are project managers, 43 (17.13%) are engineers, 52 (20.72%) are architects, 40 (15.94%) are quantity surveyors, 51 (20.32%) builders, while others are 27 (10.76%).

The experiences of the respondents in the industry consist of 32 (12.75%) of the respondents have spent 1-5 years, 45 (17.93%) spent 6-10 years, 52 (20.72%), 11-15 years, 103 (41.04%) 16-20 years, while 19 (7.57%) over 21 years.

The academic qualifications of the respondents include, 12 (4.78%) had NCE/ND as qualification. 148 (58.96%) had HND/B.Sc/B.Eng, 84 (33.47) had MBA/M.Sc as qualification, while 7 (2.79%) had Ph.Ds.

On the types of infrastructure projects executed by the respondents, the details shows that 174 (69.32%) were building related infrastructure projects, 38 (15.14%) are road related infrastructure projects, 22 (8.76%) bridge-related infrastructure projects, while other-related infrastructure projects consist of 17 (6.77%).

The sources of funding of the infrastructure projects consist of 114 (45.42%) were privately funded, while 137 (54.58) were publicly funded.

The mean ranking of the current level of awareness and extent of UAV adoption in monitoring and evaluating infrastructural projects was conducted. Based on the details, the level of awareness and extent of UAV adoption with the highest mean ranking was, "Are you aware of the capabilities of unmanned aerial vehicle in infrastructural project monitoring and evaluation?", with a "moderate" mean value of 2.40. This indicates that practitioners working on infrastructure projects are moderately aware of the capabilities of unmanned aerial vehicle in infrastructural project monitoring and evaluation. The second highest mean ranking is "Have you seen an unmanned aerial vehicle before" with a "low" mean value of 2.05, denoting that the infrastructure project practitioners have seen an unmanned aerial vehicle used to enhance infrastructure project performance. "Can you operate an unmanned aerial vehicle" ranked at the third place, with a "low" mean value of 2.01. The level of awareness and extent of UAV adoption with the least mean ranking is "Have you ever used UAV in Infrastructural Project Monitoring and Evaluation", with a "low" mean value of 1.89. Therefore, it is considered the least level of awareness and extent of UAV adoption in infrastructure projects.

5. Conclusion

from the outcomes of the results, the study concludes that; there is a low level of awareness and extent of UAV adoption in monitoring and evaluating infrastructural projects across Nigeria, given that a moderate" 2.40 mean value from the respondents are aware of the capabilities of unmanned aerial vehicle in infrastructural project monitoring and evaluation. that a "low" 2.05 mean value from the respondents have seen an unmanned aerial vehicle used to enhance infrastructure project performance. while a "low" 2.01 mean value of the respondents can operate an unmanned aerial vehicle. while, a "low" 1.89 mean value as affirmed by the respondents have ever used UAV in infrastructural project monitoring and evaluation. This study recommends that given the moderate and low levels of awareness and extent of UAV adoption in monitoring and evaluating infrastructural projects across Nigeria, there should be concerted effort geared towards ensuring that some level of intense awareness is created towards the adoption of UAV adoption in monitoring and evaluating infrastructural projects. The use of UAV and its adoption has found in routes in other climes where difficulty of accessing infrastructural projects in remote sites and locations has been addressed with minimal resources like the UAV. The communication and the entertainment industry have already keyed into to use of commercial-based UAV in photography and other entertainment-related activities. The infrastructure project-based industry should not be left out in this paradigm shift any longer.

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